

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: OCHIGBO****FIRST NAME: MARIA****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author used Microsoft inbuilt citation and bibliography to insert references

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. All these options are correct except:

- Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.
- Plagiarism is wrong and unethical.
- Having someone write a paper for you and then putting your name on it and giving it to your professor would not be plagiarism.¹**
- To avoid plagiarism, properly cite the author or source that has provided the information you are using.

2. What are Style guides?

- They are a means of documenting your approach as a writer using different style.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, , 2nd ed. 2019), 5.

- They are only associated with academic writing.
- They are essential if the finished publication is to be coherent and consistent.²**
- They are for publications or companies with a large number of contributing authors, allow authors to use their own style so they can exhibit their creativity.

3. How do you evaluate the Reliability of Online Sources?

- The site is sponsored by a reputable organization and or a reliable professional journal.³**
- Sites should be supported by individuals.
- It encouraged heated advocacy for or against a contested social issue.
- It does make wild claims, attack other researchers, use abusive language, or make errors of spelling, punctuation, and grammar.

4. What follow does readers in the experimental sciences expect?

- Introduction – literature review – method – results – discussion- Conclusion- recommendation.
- Introduction- Methods and Materials- Results- Discussion- Conclusion.⁴**
- Introduction – discussion – summary.

² Ibid., 24.

³ Kate L.Turabian . *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Revised by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams and the University of Chicago Press editorial staff- eight edition (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 9th ed. 2019) 29.

⁴ Ibid., 43.

- Executive summary – introduction – study design and setting – results – discussion – conclusion.
5. **What scenario do you Quote instead of summarizing or paraphrasing the words?**
- The exact wording constitutes evidence that backs up your reasons.**⁵
- A passage states a view that you disagree with, and to be fair you want to state it exactly.
- The quoted words are from an authority who you respect, however he/she worked on a different and unrelated topic.
- The quoted words are not original.
6. **What is a dissertation proposal?**
- A document developed and submitted for approval purpose.
- A document merely descriptive specifications of what you will do.
- A proposal is not an end in itself.
- working document on the way to the production of a dissertation.**⁶
7. **Literature review is all except one of the underlisted option:**
- The literature review identifies what is already known about your topic/problem.

⁵ Ibid., 49.

⁶ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe. 2008. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Inc. Fourth edition, 2008), 18.

- what consensus or lack there is around your topic/problem under study.
 - Literature is reviewed to identify other relevant research, so that you can situate your work in the literature, as well as draw from the literature to inform your study.
 - Literature review helps develop the argument for your study.**⁷
8. **Chapter one, which is Introduction contain following information, except:**
- Context of the study -which introduces the research by providing the background that sets the stage for the study.
 - Problem to be investigated.
 - Purpose of the study.
 - Study site and sample size.**⁸
9. **Problem, purpose and _____ are the building blocks—the very core—of your study; they are intrinsically tied together and from which everything else develops:**
- Introduction.
 - Abstract.
 - Method.
 - Research questions.**⁹

⁷ Ibid., 18 -19.

⁸ Bloomberg and Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Ibid., 33.

⁹ Ibid.

10. Use of capital letters for words should be limited and consistent throughout a publication, how should a proper names, titles and institutions be written in WHO style?

- In small letters.
- Capital letter throughout.
- Initial capital.**¹⁰
- No special style.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2nd ed. 2019.

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World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*. 20 Avenue Appia, 1211 Geneva 27, Switzerland, 2004.

¹⁰ World Health Organization. 2004. *WHO style guide*. (20 Avenue Appia, 1211 Geneva 27, Switzerland, 2004), 5.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.